

Karanja Residency and the Marathas

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Abstract- Karanja is a small island about eight miles long and four miles broad, situated at latitude 18° 15' and longitude 73° 02'. It lies about six miles south east of Carnac Pier oil Mumbai Harbour. On the east it is cut off from the main land by the Bendkhal Creek, which at high tide is inaccessible from Panvel by road. The island rises in two rocky hills, km in the north and high in the south, between which lies a strip of land wooded with mango trees and plains. To the east of the island, there are salt pans which divide the Creek into several small branches, while one arm of the Creek runs from Mora² Bunder in the north to Uran³ in the south. It is deep enough for boays to ply⁴.

Since Company's control over Mumbai they tired to possess Karanja several times.⁵ On failing which Aungier, the head of Surat factory wrote to the Directors to improve the fortification of Mumbai. In his opinion the Marathas threatened not only the trade of the Company but its very existence on the Western coast of India.⁶ He wished to enter into a defensive treaty of friendship and free trade with the Portuguese. He concluded that the safety of Mumbai depended very largely upon the neighbouring islands of Karanja and Salsette, which were the Portuguese Possessions.⁷ He, therefore, suggested that the two neighbours should act together Aungier's draft treaty contained some commercial clauses which would have conferred on the. British, the freedom of passage at Thane and Karanja. The Portuguese did not like to grant these necessary concessions for British Trade.⁸ Aungier urged the Company authority to sanction him some additional men and money so as to enable him to capture karanja⁹ finally, the Company conquered the island of Karanja in 1774 and made it a Residency.¹⁰ In the following March, the conquest of Karanja was confirmed by the Treaty of Surat¹¹, the confirmation was reaffirmed by the Treaty of Purandhar¹² in March 1776. It was finarrly ratified by the Tredy of Salbar¹³ in 1782.¹⁴

The treaty of Salbal, 1782, is an Important landmark in the History of India, Mahadji Shinde emerged as prominent member of the Maratha Confederacy, as he had personally guaranteed the proper observance of this treaty. Governor General Warren Hastings gave him a free hand in the Mughal affairs at Delhi, However, the growing friendship between. Hastings and Mahadji was looked upon with suspicion by other members of the Confederacy for some time.¹⁵

After the first Anglo-marath war the Company authorities maintained cordial relations with the Peshwa and other members of the Maratha Confederacy and avoided taking up any controversial issue with them. However, this cordiality did not last long. On 8 April 1783, 'Rangers under the commandant of Lt. Puren a small British vessel carrying twelve guns was attacked by the Maratha ships off the coast of Ratnagiri, while on its way to Calicut, 5 British officers, 28 sepoy and 8 injured. Anantrao Dhulap, the traditional naval chief of the Marathas captured five British ships and detained them at Vijaydurg¹⁶ Enraged Company officials complained to Mahadji Shinde about the high handed action of the Marathas who held Nana Phadnavis responsible for it, Nana then released the captured British ship and goods and further compensated the British for whatever loss they had suffered during the attack. The matter was thus settled amicably¹⁷.

Inspite of the Treaty of Salbai Raghunathrao continued to remain under British protection at Surat. Inspite or repeated requests ,of Nana and Mahadji Shinde the Company authorities refused to

hand Raghunathrao over to their. Meanwhile. Raghunathrao continued to insist upon the Company authorities that they restore him to Peshwaship. He also sent his representatives. Hanmantao and Marriort to Landon to represent his case before the British government but they had to return empty handed after having spent one year in London. A trustrated and disappointed Raghunathrao died on 11 December 1783 at Kopargaon leaving behind his widow and three sons. Thus, a Major factor in the anglo-Maratha conflict was eliminated.¹⁸

Inspite of his profession of friendship with Mahadji, Warren Hasting's tried to counter his growing influence in the Mughal Emperor and offer his the financial and other help. But the Emperor refused to respond to the Maj. Browns offer, Warrne Hanstigns then went to Lucknow and camped there for a long time with a view to persuade the Emperor to accept British help. Mahadji Shinde obviously did not like Hasting's interference in the Mughal affaris. He therefore protested to Hastings who then offered some lame excuse saying that the Mughal prince Jawan Bakht was pressing him to espouse the Emperor's case against the Marathas.¹⁹

The Treaty of Salbai put the marathas under an obligation to help the company authorities to recover their former territories in Karnataka from haidar All Meanwhile, Tipu Sultan had replaced Haidar Ali on the latter's death on 7 December 1782. The Company authorities then sent General Mathews with a British force to Malabar. Although initially General Mathews with a British force to Malabar. Although initially General Mathews was able to

capture Honawar and Mangalore on his way to Malabar later he was decisively defeated by Tipu Sultan. The Company authorities were then forced to sign the Treaty of Mangalore with Tipu without consulting either Nana or Mahadji. The treaty gave the Company authorities a temporary respite, it proved to be a short-lived treaty.²⁰

In July 1785 a British ship 'Rodney' was on its way from Mumbai to China with some cargo. Bad weather and rough sea compelled it to seek shelter in the Maratha port of Gheria, where its captain and crew members were arrested and goods thereon were plundered by the Marathas. The ship was badly damaged, it could not proceed further without extensive repairs. This was a clear violation of the Treaty of Salbai on the part of the Marathas.²¹

When Hastings resigned on 12 September 1786, Lord Cornwallis succeeded him as the Governor General of India. In the meanwhile Tipu Sultan was found conspiring with the French against the British in India. Cornwallis was therefore determined to defeat Tipu with a view to forming an alliance against Tipu. Cornwallis instructed Resident Malet²² at Poona to negotiate an alliance with the Marathas. Malet had lengthy consultations with the Mumbai Governor about the nature of the proposed alliance between 29 March and 11 April 1788. However, Nana soon realized that other members of the Maratha Confederacy were reluctant to accept any alliance against Tipu Sultan, who in their opinion, could effectively check the growing British power in India. Later, mainly because of Malet's persistent efforts a treaty was concluded between the British and the Marathas on 1 July 1790 at Poona in terms of which forts and territory conquered in the ensuing war with Tipu to be divided equally among them.²³

Soon thereafter a Maratha contingent of soldiers under Parshuram Bhau joined the British army under Cornwallis, in a joint action they defeated Tipu but could not crush him completely. Meanwhile, under instructions from the London authorities, Cornwallis was forced to conclude a peace treaty with Tipu on 11 February 1792.²⁵ Thereafter Tipu secretly met the Maratha commander and tried to convince him that the British and not he were their real enemy. Tipu also cautioned the Maratha commander against the British.²⁵

Later Parshuram Bhau, and Nana sought Cornwallis's help against Mahadji Shinde but Cornwallis refused to do so since Mahadji was a friend of the British as it turned out, sharp differences between Nana Phadnavis and Mahadji prevented the Marathas from taking any concerted action against the British in India.²⁶

Malet continued as British Resident at Poona up to 1797, endeared himself to a young Peshwa and witnessed many changes which took place at the Poona court during this period, he advised both Cornwallis and John Shore to follow a policy of

patience towards the Marathas while Nana and Mahadji were on the scene.²⁷

Mahadji Shinde died on 12 February 1794 at Wanawadi after a brief illness. Some days before his death he had adopted Daulatrao, a 14-year-old son of his cousin. To John Shore Mahadji's death meant a favourable turn of events for the British.²⁸ For he had effectively checked their ambition in the Mughal court and had not liked the Anglo-Maratha alliance against Tipu. He also wanted the Marathas to have close relations with Tipu.²⁹ On 27 October 1795 Peshwa Sawai Makhavrao jumped to his death.³⁰ From the first floor of the Shanwar Wada. Since he died without an issue he should have been succeeded, by one of his cousins Bajirao, Chimnaji & Amritrao sons of Raghunathrao, however, Nana was opposed to all of them. He therefore proposed that the late Peshwa's widow Yashodabai should adopt a son in whose name he would carry on the administration.³¹ Nana's plan was opposed by other members of the Confederacy. On 26 November 1796, Baloba Tatya, Daulatrao's representative, informed Malet about Daulatrao's opposition to Nana's plan. But Malet refused to commit himself in favour of either Mahadji or Bajirao since the British were obliged to follow a strict neutral policy.³²

Later, Daulatrao agreed to help Bajirao in his attempt to secure Peshwaship in return for Rs.1,25,00,000 in cash and jagir worth Rs. 25,00,000/ per annum.³³

When Nana came to know about this plan he decided to make Chimnaji the Peshwa and retain the administration with himself. He then informed Malet of his plan and sought his support.³⁴ Nana then dispatched Parshuram Bhau to Shivner fort to escort Chimnaji back to Poona but Bajirao strongly opposed Parshuram Bhau who had to return empty-handed to Poona. Nana was then compelled to accept Bajirao as the Peshwa Bajirao II as he was popularly known, was the eldest son of Raghunathrao.³⁵

Bajirao had spent most of his formative years in jail and so he did not have the necessary training or experience to assume the onerous responsibility of the office of Peshwa. He was therefore bound to face many problems and difficulties. The most immediate and pressing problem before him was the one about his agreement with Daulatrao in terms of which he had to give Daulatrao Rs.1,25,00,000/- in cash and jagir worth Rs. 25,00,000/- per annum. After he became the Peshwa. However, Bajirao refused to honour his agreement on one pretext or the other.³⁶ Taking advantage of Bajirao's absence from Poona, Daulatrao managed to install Chimnaji as the Peshwa on 12 May 1796.³⁷ Although both Nana and Malet knew about Daulatrao's plan Bajirao himself was completely in the dark about it.³⁸

However, Nana refused to acknowledge Chimnaji as the new Peshwa. He also claimed that most of the members of the Confederacy were vehemently

opposed to Chimnaji becoming peshwa. He also sought Malet's help in installing Bajirao in the office of Peshwa for which he was ready to cede to the British territory worth Rs.25,00,000/- per annum. However, the company authorities refused to interfere in the internal affairs of the Marathas.³⁹

In July 1796, Nana inflicted a decisive defeat on Daulatrao with the help of Tukoji Holkar and Raghujji Bhosale. He had promised to pay them Rs.15,00,000/- each for their help.⁴⁰ On 25 November 1796 Nana convened a meeting of all members of the confederacy to seek their support for Bajirao's Peshwaship and Naro Chakradeo, the Commander-in-Chief.⁴¹

After the death of Tukoji Holkar, Nana supported Malharrao, his second son in place of Kashirao, the eldest son who was an imbecile. Later Daulatrao put to death Malharrao, arrested Nana on 31st December 1796 and put him in Ahmadnagar jail.⁴² In the meanwhile Sarjerao, Diwan and father-in-law of Daulatrao went on rampage in Poona in an attempt to collect the money which Bajirao had promised him.⁴³ Amritrao then caused Daulatrao to be arrested and forced him to leave Poona.⁴⁴

Finding himself in a difficult situation Daulatrao released Nana and sought his friendship to counter Bajirao and Amritrao. Nana agreed to pay him Rs.10,00,000/- in return for his release from the Ahmadnagar prison.⁴⁵ Nana was badly shaken by his brief imprisonment. Although he continued to discharge his duties he was unable to bear the humiliation and insults which Daulatrao had inflicted on him. He became a physical and mental wreck, his health started deteriorating. On 13 March 1800, he died.⁴⁵

Nana's death removed all restraint on Daulatrao because of which Bajirao's position became precarious.

Moreover, Yashwantrao Holkar and many other Maratha chiefs supported Amritrao in his attempt to become the Peshwa.⁴⁷

Amritrao then invited Yashwantrao Holkar to Poona with a view to pressurize Bajirao to give up the Peshwaship. On 8 October 1802 Yashwantrao Holkar defeated Bajirao's forces at Baramati which caused a panic in Poona.⁴⁸

Scared of his insecure position Bajirao left Poona to seek shelter at Mahad from where he was escorted to Vasai on 17 December 1802 where he was received by Col. Close.⁴⁹ He then signed the famous Treaty of Vasai with Col. Close on 31 December 1802. It was ratified by the Governor General on 18 March 1803.⁵⁰

Both Amritrao and Yashwantrao were very much disappointed by this treaty, especially as it provided that Bajirao should be restored to the Peshwaship. Yashwantrao felt that the British would treat Bajirao the same way as they had treated Tipu Sultan.⁵¹

Col. Close then wrote to Yashwantrao that in terms of this treaty Bajirao would soon be restored to Peshwaship and Yashwantrao should go away from Poona if he wanted his grievances against Bajirao to be redressed by the company authorities.⁵² Yashwantrao left Poona for the north on 13 March 1803 which Amritrao went to Junnar and requested Col. Close to pressurize Bajirao to grant Amritrao a suitable pension. Bajirao arrived in Poona on 13 May 1803, to assume the Peshwaship. The occasion was celebrated for a number of days by the Maratha chiefs with much pomp and show.⁵³

References

1. The Gazetteer of India Maharashtra state Gazetteers, Kolaba District P. 911
2. Mendoca J.N. Topography of the island of Karanja current & Mecentile Register Press, Bombay, 1868, P.11
3. Gazetteers of India, Maharashtra State Gazetteer, Kolaba District, P. 1112,
4. Mendoca, op.cit, PP. 1-6
5. W.S. Desai, Baomay and the Marathas, Munishiram Manoharlal, Delhi 1970, P.14
6. James Douglas, Bombay and Western India, Samson Law and Martson, London, Vo. II. P. 178.
7. S.M. Edward (ed.) The Gazetteer of Bombay City and Island. Vol I. Times Press, Bombay, 1909, P. 62.
8. Ibid, P. 89
9. W.S. Desai, op.cit, P.16.
10. P.D. General Order Book, No.4, Mumbai p.110, Karanja Residency Record, Inward Letter dated 28 August, 1775, p5
11. G.S. Sardesai, New History of Marathas, Phoenix Publication, Bombay, 1948 Vol. III, P.P. 49.50
12. H.H. Dodwell, The Cambridge History of India, S.Chand & Company Vol. P.P. 260, 261
13. G.S. Sardesai, op. Cit. Vol. III, P.P. 111, 119.
14. Gazetteers of India, Maharashtra State, Gazetteer, Kolaba District, P. 820.
15. Forest, Op. Cit, Vol. III, P. 978.
16. Vijaydurg or Geria fort is about 170 miles south of Mumbai, it is a port in the Devgad Taluka of Sindhudurg district, in 1698, Konoji Angre made it the capital of a territory stretching far about 150 miles along the coast, in 1756, the fort was abandoned by the British under admiral Watson and Col. Clive took possession of it towards the close of the same year, it was handed over to the Peswas in exchange of Bankot. Imperial Gazetteers of Bombay Presidency, Vol. II p.170, and Khare, Althasik Lekh Sangrah, Vol. IX. Bhan

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| <p>17. Sardesai, G.S. Op. Cit, VI III, P.122</p> <p>18. G.S. Sardesai, O. cit, PP 124-127</p> <p>19. H.H. Dodwell, Letters of Warren Hastings, S.Chand & Co. 1930 P. 193.</p> <p>20. J.C. Marshman, Op. Cit., Vol. I.P. 410.</p> <p>21. Secret and Political Dairy No.32, Letter dated 8 February, 1785. p.10</p> <p>22. Malet was born in 1752 and entered the company service in 1770, as a writer at Mumbai. He was posted at the factory of Cambay in 1755, Where he helped Raghoba who proceeded in British ship, to Surat and subsequently concluded the treaty on Surat with the British. The treaty gave rise to the first Anglo-Maratha War. His diplomatic intercourse with the Maratha Government in ten long year of his residency succeeded In weakening the Marathas cohesion and enhanced the British prestige and power. He was the first British statesman to give the Marathas a forestate of all sided western penetration. G.S. Sardesai, Op. cit. Vol III, P. 196.</p> <p>23. D.B. Parasnis, Poona in Bygone Days, The Times Press, Bombay, 1921 p. 40.</p> <p>24. H.H. Dodwell, Op. Cit. Vol. V.P. 337</p> <p>25. G.S. Sardesai, Op. Cit., p. 192</p> <p>26. Ibid., P. 194</p> <p>27. Poona Residency Correspondency, Vol II P. 311</p> | <p>28.</p> <p>29.</p> <p>30.</p> <p>31.</p> <p>32.</p> <p>33.</p> <p>34.</p> <p>35.</p> <p>36.</p> <p>37.</p> <p>38.</p> <p>39.</p> <p>40.</p> <p>41.</p> <p>42.</p> <p>43.</p> <p>44.</p> <p>45.</p> <p>46.</p> <p>47.</p> <p>48.</p> <p>49.</p> <p>50.</p> <p>52.</p> <p>53.</p> | <p>S.N. Sen. Anglo-Maratha Relations. P. 184</p> <p>P.E. Robert, History of British India Under the Company and the Crown, Oxford Oxford University Press, Oxford 1938, p. 240</p> <p>Khare, Aitiasic Lekha Sangraha, Vol. IX, Letter No.3644</p> <p>Grant Duff, Op. Cit., Vol. II p. 257</p> <p>G.S. Sardesai, PRC, Voll II, p.401.</p> <p>Grant Duff, Op. cit, Vol II, P. 256.</p> <p>Khare. Op. Cit. Vol IX, Letter No. 3662</p> <p>Ibid., No. 3663</p> <p>Khare, Op. Cit., Vol IX, Letter No.3732</p> <p>Ibid., Letter No. 3784</p> <p>Ibid., Letter No. 3730</p> <p>Ibid., Letter No. 3784</p> <p>Grant Duff, Po. cit. p.267</p> <p>Ibid., P. 270</p> <p>Grant Duff. Op. cit., p.273</p> <p>Ibid., p. 274</p> <p>Ibid., p. 277</p> <p>Ibid., p. 285</p> <p>G.S. Sardesai, Po. cit.p. 357</p> <p>Khare Op. cit., Letter No. 6387, and PRC Vol. X,p. VIII</p> <p>Khare Op. cit., Letter No. 6461</p> <p>G.S. Sardesai, Op. cit., p. 380</p> <p>Aitchison, Op. cit. p.p. 55-58</p> <p>Forest, State Papers, p. 596</p> <p>Reghubir Singh, PRC VOI X. Sri Gouranga Press, Calcutta, 1951, p. XVII.</p> |
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